

**“ I WENT TO HEAVEN AND DIDN'T SEE GOD THERE ”: MAJOR
YURI GAGÁRIN'S PUERIL DECEPTION**

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ABSTRACT

This essay presents the issue involving the emblematic phrase attributed to Yuri Gagarin, a Soviet astronaut who was the first human being to go to space, in which he claims not to have seen God. What is sought to address in this discussion is the gnosiological dimension that is hidden under such a statement to what extent it can be attributed and attributed to the Major. It is very common for contextualized expressions to be attributed to figures that have become controversial throughout history, without anyone standing up to equalize the dimension of the exposed. This is an exploratory research, based on the principles of discourse analysis, content analysis and hermeneutics, in which we sought to understand the blank spaces left for all these decades around a subject of such complexity. What can be concluded, after all the systematic study that involved him, is that it makes no sense for someone who has all human feats in courage and determination, going to outer space and glimpsing his home from above, worrying It is said that he had not seen God, unless this was an answer to a poorly worded and poorly worded question. With a semantic study character, what is intended to present here is a hermeneutic analysis of the sentence, supposedly said by the astronaut, in which from the linguistic analytical point of view, it is not supported as being authored by Major Russo Yuri Gagarin. From the point of view of human interpretation, from the most primitive human beings to the most brilliant scientist, this has always been a question that challenges everyone, going through the ancestral totemic construction, in which the adored God cannot be found, never seen and those who encountered him, they were caught up into infinity.

Keywords: Yuri Gagarin; Cold War; Space race; Faith.

INTRODUCTION

Figures that become legendary for their extraordinary deeds and end up turning into mythical creatures, for having performed an action that was, until he appeared, only a product

of the social imagination, he is forced to carry quite heavy burdens, especially if he belongs to a regime that is considered diabolical, satanic and that rivals another that hides behind an aura of chastity and sanctity and that, to inflame the vanity and ego of those who attack and who receives the attack, receives as a sentence a challenge that sounds much more like a direct threat.

Yuri Aleksevitch Gagarin (1934-1968) is one of these human beings, condemned to immortality, for being the first man [*and not the first biological being*] to see the Earth from outer space. When, after a brilliant trajectory in the Armed Forces of the [Former] Soviet Union, he was chosen to man the spacecraft Vostok - 1, which would orbit the Earth's atmosphere. One of his famous phrases that went down in history was: "The Earth is blue", a fact that would go through proof and refutation years later, when Project Apollo was concluded, which would take an American crew to the Moon.

In all the ways that I have tried to analyze this sentence by Gagarin, it does not seem to come from his own mouth, looking more like a well-assembled construction spoken by someone in conflict and who took advantage of the feat, unparalleled at the time, to criticize the West. Christian. Because, an atheist it is very likely that he was and would hardly be able to lie to his Russian superiors for so long, being from an early age formed and trained in military colleges of high excellence, under extreme tension and training pressure regarding character and personological structure.

What conflicts with Gagarin's stance is the fact that the way it was expressed could hide a Soviet desire to find out if really God was there in the heavens, dwelling beyond the earth's atmosphere. This cannot be doubted, because the most the Russians have done [*and their pioneering advances in this field cannot be underestimated*] is to orbit the Earth, with a human crew. Therefore, if this was the main motivation of the mission of the spacecraft Vostok - 1, which took Major Yuri Gagarin to the skies, his speech is nothing more than the reporting of the conclusion of a mission to his immediate superiors, which exempts the astronaut of any moral judgment about his particular beliefs and his faith, not being able to attribute to this speech any value whatsoever that could determine who Major Gagarin was as to his state of belief.

Every time one tries to understand the semantic meaning of the sentence, using all the discourse analysis tools that are available, there is no guideline that can safely obtain a gnosiological meaning for it, because it leaves the impression free. that it would have to be someone materialist to the extreme to believe in something like that, implying that the phrase came from a scientist dedicated to empirical research, willing to apply the full power of the

principle of verifiability and refutability to such a thought. You are not arguing with someone who accepts the speech as an answer to some epic question.

Colonel Valentin Petrov stated, in the year 2006, during an interview, that the cosmonaut never said such words, and that the quote originated from the speech of Nikita Khrushchev (1894-1971) in the plenary of the Central Committee of the CPSU about the anti-war campaign. - State religion. The then president of the [Former] USSR argued against his comrades, why did they believe in the existence of God, since Major Gagarin had gone to heaven and had looked everywhere and had not seen God there, this during a speech before the Central Committee of the Soviet Communist Party in which anti-religious propaganda was discussed.¹⁹

Put in this way, it is not very difficult to understand the meaning it carries and the decision of the Communist Political Committee to attribute to the only man, until that moment in history, to clear the cosmic space, a feat that would be equaled, in 1963, by a wife, Valentina Vladimirovna Tereshkova. But it doesn't matter, because the Politburo's interest was to show its unrivaled and unsurpassed strength, no matter what tactics and strategies they were. Throughout history, the respected cosmonaut had to bear the weight of value judgments about something unsaid, no matter what he thought about or even what he replied to his superiors when questioned about the issue in particular.

With the character of a semantic study, what we intend to present here is a hermeneutic analysis of the said sentence, in which from the linguistic analytical point of view, it is not supported as being authored by Major Russo Yuri Gagarin, as already discussed briefly in this preamble. But from the point of view of human interpretation, from the most primitive human beings to the most brilliant scientist, this has always been a question that challenges everyone, going through the ancestral totemic construction, in which the adored God cannot be found, never seen and never seen. those who encountered him were caught up to infinity. Even among Brazilian folklore there is a legend that closely narrates this situation. The legend of the water lily is about the Indian woman who wanted to find the Moon Knight and dives into the waters of the Amazon River in search of him and disappears, possibly having found him. In Greek mythology, Hera jealous of Semele, a mortal who was pregnant with Dionysus, son of her union with Zeus, convinces her to ask for the Father of the Gods to manifest in his original form and once the unusual request is granted, she is pulverized by the Intense glow of God. Thus, the

¹⁹ There is a reference to this interview in the book *Talking Well : Touch People with Your Words*, by Charles R. Swindoll, originally published in English in 2012 by FaithWords Hachette Book Grup, New York, USA and an edition in Portuguese , by the CPAD, of 2017.

urge to see God manifest is a feeling that dominates human beings since their earliest existential childhood on the Planet.

What is brought in this work is the possibility of thinking about the existence of the Sacred from faith and that materialism tried, using all existing tactics and that creativity can process in the light of reason and imagination, to prove otherwise. Not believing in the existence of God is everyone's right, not implying an act of lack of ethics, since human beings are allowed to freely exercise their faith. The problem becomes interesting and becomes an object of systematic study when conflict arises and this acts betraying the [*supposed presence of*] individual faith or the [*alleged*] absence of it, in the role of human existence.

Working on purely didactic purposes, under the psychoanalytic aspect, the text will use the phrase expressed as being authored by Major Gagarin. Let the reader be aware that this is a high-level scientific study and not a mere conjuncture of ideas, disguising proselytizing of any kind. The author clearly expresses all his respect to the Russian Cosmonaut for his avant-garde act in aerospace exploration.

GAGARIN AND HIS EMBLEMATIC AND CONTROVERSIAL PHRASE

When Russian astronaut Major Yuri Gagarin (*Yuri Alekseievitch Gagarin* [1934-1968]) released the phrase: “I went to heaven and did not see God”, in April 1961, he was shaken by public opinion, calling him an inveterate atheist and, until the present day, some spirits devoid of any critical sense and erudite knowledge. tend to judge and condemn him for this sentence, completely decontextualizing his expression. In fact, no one knows in what real context it was said and if it was even expressed by the Major. And the worst thing about it all is that [*almost*] no one stops to try to analyze the situation, in order to approach a deduction about its gnosiological meaning.

However, his sentence, when analyzed under the stigma of being the first man in the history of humanity to ascend to cosmic space, expresses [*much*] more an outburst in the face of an unprecedented disappointment, similar to the outburst of a child who anxiously awaits the her father arrives and when the train stops at the station and everyone gets off she looks at her mother and says with a mixed look of sadness, disappointment and questioning [*about*] why ' *daddy didn't come!?* '. The original phrase is: “ *I looked everywhere, but I did not see God!*”

Even if the sentence came from a [*supposed*] convinced atheist, which due to its dimension does not match, because an atheist who is convinced of his faith in the denial of the existence of the divine essence would give another answer to whoever questioned him, unless

the questioner was an officer of a higher rank than his own, to whom he owed an obligation to be clear and objective in his answer. Otherwise, this answer that seems to be so well formulated was created in the midst of a contextual situation of questions and answers, where the textual set resulted in the same.

But the shrill of this phrase is much greater and more potent than it itself and all its meaning for materialistic belief, making much more echo among those who call themselves devout Christians and who have learned to have faith by tradition and not by a process. doctrinal and disciplinary training. In contrast, no members of atheist groups were seen to make use of it in order to strengthen their theses that God does not exist.

Let's start at the beginning: someone who, in fact, does not believe in the existence of God, does not create theses to argue with those who believe [*or who supposes to believe in the Divine Essence*], because this individual conviction does not allow the existence of any kind of internal conflict. ; therefore, there is nothing to generate and maintain any kind of external conflict, that is, it is easier to find doubts about the real existence of God among those who believe and what may seem like a terrible paradox is nothing more than a human condition, in that belief generates needs for countless other types of complementary elements, such as faith, for example, patience, effort and perseverance, attributes that are not part of the human being until one has been properly educated to do so.

Following this, it is necessary to consider the fact that, as one deepens the understanding of *Episteme* and *phrónesis* , all the ability to interpret the *Physis* that is being raised transforms the human being and, if one does not have the proper metaphysical preparation, begins to think that he can give answers to everything that surrounds him and, in a short time, he believes himself to be the absolute ruler of the universe that surrounds him and of what he can see, until he begins to take as his own, everything he can imagine, ignoring that everything, in its brute form, was already given, not being able to create anything, only to apply his intellect to material goods and transform them into other useful and necessary things for him, because he translated his inability to live in accordance with the laws and goods of nature as dissatisfaction, which is nothing more than the expression of a euphemism that hides his inability to adapt to Nature. Thus, he distorts it until it adapts to what he is and when he achieves such a feat, he interprets his feat as competence, when in fact this is the sovereign expression of all his incompetence before the natural, before *Physis* .

A scientist, trained in the classical molds of Erudite Science, will never make a statement that prejudices the belief of his opponents, because for this being, the conflict is not set in the sense of winning his *supposed* imaginary enemies, but rather, in the case of a contemplation of

the search for scientific truth that, at most, brings him closer and closer to a broader and deeper understanding of the phenomena that occur in nature. Knowing that a scientific discovery, however innovative it appears and even if it proves to be, only demonstrates that what was believed before it was true or false; but it does not prove that it is itself true. With his presentation, he does nothing more than provide space for new academic and scientific discussions, now in new directions and Gagarin, being a technician trained in the classic Soviet molds, was fully aware of this epistemological and gnosiological dimension of the sciences.

Furthermore, it was a moment of the Cold War when the scientific community was interested in the discovery of space and the exploration of it, and the existence or non-existence of God did not make the slightest difference, because man was taking very important steps in directions that, a few years ago, rather, it was thought to be impossible, because it was not endowed by nature or by its Creator with specific capacities that would allow it to go beyond the world that it was conditioned to live and to know, through empirical experience. Everything, in addition to this, would only be possible to know through the experience of imagination and, suddenly, this field is solidified, from the development of engineering and man can experience new opportunities for experiences never before thought, in the history of humanity.

One was not being transformed into God with this, or even as Nietzsche would claim, killing him, so that he could go beyond his limits, because in admitting such a thing, he reveals an inconsequential adolescent behavior, as if he were affirming the theory. of Fyodor Dostoevsky, that if God does not exist, then everything becomes permissible.²⁰

Few understand that this thought is like what is usually said to be the ability to miss what has never lived, except in a phylogenetic condition and not even in an ontogenetic condition, except for those bizarre thoughts that extrapolate a level of reason that one does not have, as is the case with the representation of childhood and its personological developments.

To advocate the existence of a world without the presence of God is to return to the state of barbarism, at the time that T. Hobbes classifies as the *State of Nature*, in which everything was allowed to everyone, with no limits to the satisfaction of desires and, in this space described by the English thinker, there was a need to create an order that was placed above all men, so that peace could exist, understanding it as an [*unstable*] balance between the pleasure principle and the reality principle. .

²⁰ This is a very complex and difficult to understand passage present in DOSTOYEVSKI's book, Feódor Mikhailovich. *The Karamazov Brothers*. vol. 3. Rio de Janeiro: Livraria José Olympio publisher, 1955 (3 vol.), p. 1118-1119.

And, suddenly, there is a realization that God would not be in the heights, that is, if he were not up there, above the clouds; where could it be? This is the question that was posed, because if the expectation with this statement was that it would destroy a whole set of beliefs in a superior being, whoever said it just showed the most absurd ignorance about the human psyche, especially if this is the mind of a scientist of the stature of Gagarin.

BETWEEN BELIEF AND UNBELIEVABLE: WHAT A SCIENTIST LOOKS FOR

A scientist does not look for what he does not believe exists, dedicating his time to know the dictates of the phenomena and himself within a narrow interstice between what is explained and what is not yet explained, raising hypotheses that allow an approximation each time. with the truth and that can explain the occurrence of events, in a deeper or more superficial way and with each discovery, this does not eliminate the possibility that there are other answers, only that he himself did not find them in his searches.

The problem with the Soviet system is that it tried at all costs to eliminate any belief in any element other than the Soviet Communist Party, while trying to make people believe that God dwelt in the Politburo ²¹and from there discharged all his bile onto the Russian people; however, in his view, he was offering the people a condition of life beyond what they could even dream of, in terms of perfection and equality, because to speak of equanimity was an outrage to a [so] perfect system.

This was the most brutal mistake that the Soviet Revolution managed to commit, believing that a whole life history that runs through the phylogenetic structure can be eliminated from the human being, ie, it does not depend on the individual, it is something intrinsic to the species to which it belongs, where the Father cannot be replaced by an abstract system. And, in the counter-defense of this, if someone dares to say that God is abstract, he may even be, but the faith that is placed in his person is not, and even if someone says that he does not exist, because he cannot be seen, this is not matter, because what is sought is hope in better days, in a better tomorrow and even if it takes time to present itself, the human being continues to sustain itself by this faith, because through the same structure that guides the species, there is another that leads the individual, ontogenetics, in which the being itself repeats, in adult life, everything that it has experienced in its childhood, as if there were two distinct existences in itself.

²¹ Central Committee of the Communist Party of the former USSR

The *Soviet establishment* dared to disregard all this, believing that it could be a unique object in the lives of Russian citizens, eliminating any kind of affective bond with existence that was not offered by the State. They failed to the point that an ex-seminarian is the one who will be the most satanic dictator in the history of the former USSR, which reveals that, despite all the witch-hunt carried out against religions, faith in a Higher Being remained alive in the population and even if Yosef Stalin, had his critics to the religion, never dared to attempt against the faith, putting the existence of God in check; he just used what he learned in his seminary days very well, in favor of building a type of government where everyone [*without any distinction*] lived, constantly, under a *Sword of Damocles* .

“I went to heaven and didn't see God!” This expression, which they maliciously transformed into an atheist phrase, can be interpreted more as a way of expressing a lifetime in search of this moment, not to become the first man to explore outer space, but to see God. in person. This not happening, he lost himself in a daydream as if he were asking: “where is God? Where did it go? Did he run away from me? Why can't I see him?” I want to see you! I came here just for this; to see you!

The human urge to meet the sacred, especially when there is not a strong connection with the *Father* , is a phenomenological issue that is very present in human beings and becomes more powerful in the systems of the Iron Curtain, where individuals are oppressed by a super powerful state ideology of obscured parenting and this crushes the vertical human relationship between parents and biological children, because since Big Father (The State) and not Big Brother, as Orwell fantasized, is the one who occupies this phylogenetic space, the father biological becomes the little father and the relationship with the children becomes something horizontal. This is the problem situation that the human psyche is unable to resolve and the next step, as a consequence of the conflict arising from this artificially imposed relationship, is insanity and delinquency, resulting in serious conflicts of a spiritual nature, creating, in time, no too long, an entire society sickened and in search of a superior being to comfort it, spiritually.

The expression used, if actually uttered by the Russian Head of State, only demonstrates the immense failed work that the Soviet regime *had* to eliminate the idea of God from the popular imagination. But, in Nietzsche's writings, there is a very strong statement that serves as an explanation for this spiritual conflict that has been transformed throughout history as an emblematic clash, coming from the Soviet communists. This is the aphorism 289, present in the work *Beyond Good and Evil*, where it says that every man who ventures to express a philosophical thought knows that “behind his cave there is another cave, even deeper – a wider world, stranger, richer than on the surface, a depth behind every bottom, under every *foundation*

. Every philosophy is a philosophy of the surface. [...] Every philosophy hides another philosophy; every opinion is a hiding place, every word a new mask.”²²

Since Lenin, the Soviet Union has tried to eliminate the idea of an entity superior to itself, because the power project that was imagined by the powerful Bolshevik Party was to take the entire nation and the entire individual spirit for itself, as an object of absolute control. and, when he finds himself unable to achieve this, he appeals to all kinds of figures of speech and thought, persecuting religious people and all kinds of individuals who dared to face the Regime and its abstract way of thinking.

get a little dark when the *Stablistment* accepts as Head of State, a religious, an altar boy, candidate for Priest, who came to be baptized as Iron Man. Two things are implied there and the first is that if the Regime did so it is because the idea of eliminating God from the human imagination of the Soviets was not something already sentenced and given as reality and this caused several confusions within the structural thinking of the Politburo , which led Stalin to become one of the greatest executioners in the history of mankind and creating a system of government that not only aroused terror in Russians, but provoked horror throughout history, during his own government and after him and, to disgrace of the regime, Communism came to be confused with Stalinism. The situation Stalin got into is not difficult to understand, because being educated in the Christian doctrinal regime, in which life, faith, obedience to God the Father are advocated and, suddenly, this child who needed to prove to his peers that had the *Regime* above all, he needs to create a monstrous system of persecution and mass extermination, even of his companions, just to prove that he had not been converted by the Christian-religious faith.

There was more, no one trusted that Stalin had converted to Communism, precisely because of his religious background; therefore, the challenge was set and he knew, very well, that he was waiting for a small slip of his to confront and demoralize him in the face of *the Soviet Leninist-Marxist Doctrine* . Many hated Stalin for his arrogance; however, in his madness to erase faith in God from his life and from the popular imagination, he made the people worship him and not Mother Russia or the Communist Party, instead of God.

Thinking about the iconic and historic phrase that they put in Major Gagarin's mouth, as being uttered by President Nikita Sergeyevitch Khrushchev, demonstrates the continued contempt for his predecessor, in this question of the existence of God, because Stalin could want to overcome Him, but he would never deny its existence, even in the face of his opponents

²² NIETZSCHE, F. *Beyond good and evil*. São Paulo: Escala, 2006, p. 220. [Aphorism 289].

within the Political Communist Party; at most, avoiding touching the subject when it arose in the intense useless discussions of the Committee.

All you can see is that the phrase has a childlike character, in which one tries to forcefully prove that one was right about something that had been causing heated clashes for a long time. Unfortunately, the level of understanding of those who came later is deplorable and they did not bother to study the content of the message in depth, seeking to synthesize what is in fact between the lines of the expressed thought. And on the other hand, there are the rogues who only know how to do this, not taking the trouble to go deeper in the sense of clarifying what variables are implicit under the expression and what elements it brings so that one can, at least, understand what is going on. at the head of a system that struggled throughout its existence against the idea of the existence of an entity that was superior to itself. It seems more like a tantrum of a son who could not overcome a despotic father in his childhood and adolescence and who grew up and continued to be infantilized in his intellectual aspects.

By declaring such a sentence, the Soviet Leader ridicules the Russian astronomical mission, imagining that he is proving to everyone that the ideologues of the Soviet Communist Party were correct in an insignificant detail from the point of view of the construction of national sovereignty; which is clear that he was more at the center of vanity and pride than even managing a system as broad and complex as the Soviet nation.

When Freud created Psychoanalysis, the Soviet Union was the first nation in the world to translate the writings of the Master of Vienna into a foreign language, imagining that, with the discovery of the unconscious, a door was opened to the domain of the human being, through his psychological system over which he had no control. It would be enough for the *Establishment* to control this unexplored psychic paradise that, *voilà*, would have sovereignty over all men and women who would follow all the commandments and ordinances without even, at least and never, thinking about it. Thus, the Russians would be able to eliminate from the human being, the disease that Nietzsche attributes to the human being as the worst of all, the *bad conscience*, the *guilt*.

Paranoid pride is a serious problem for the ideologues of communism and those who join it, not resisting the idea that there may be contributions from other parties to the construction of anyone's personological structure. This causes them a repressed feeling of impotence, in which the attitude of others condemns them to see themselves as failures and this is something unacceptable. The ideology they use to present themselves as deified figures is that everything they do is for the benefit of the other, therefore, this other cannot have someone

else who is more important than him; moreover, devotion must be absolute, because all others are your enemies who only want to exploit you.

Therefore, the Soviet-Communist problem with religion goes far beyond Marx's criticism of it, when he stated that it was the opium of the people, this observation having much more a close condition with a criticism of the posture of religions in the face of the oppression that the capitalist system imposed it on everyone and the priests and pastors sought to make all those massacred by the perverse reality understand all that as being the expression of God's will towards man, because the meek of spirit would see God and with the sentence [*surreptitious, implied*] that the oppressors would be condemned, this made the wretched feel relieved, because they would be avenged, one day, by God.

For the *Communist Establishment*, there can be nothing and no one that is beyond or above it in the popular imagination. It was this same superb vanity that led them all around the world to moral disgrace. It is not recommended a living being that does not seek security, in its most complex moments, in a totemic being that is outside its vision, above and beyond its domain. As it is a structure that cannot be materialized in the human mechanical vision, what remains is faith, what is seen reflected in the numerous constructions and achievements and not only in the superficial indoctrination of a system, which preaches one thing and shows itself in a different way. deformed, as if everything and everyone were obliged to honor him, simply because he defends an idea of equality and acts like that, even though this [*alleged*] equality is a dystopian utopia.

Infantilism is the idea of believing that one can prove the existence or not of a being, simply by saying that whoever went to the extreme hasn't seen him there. To begin with, you can either have seen or not seen and these two situations do not prove or justify absolutely anything, because in science, without the verifiability condition and, *a posteriori*, without the refutability condition, everything is nothing but delusions, which can be accepted or can be refuted, on the basis of faith. It was this subtle condition that Soviet Communism and its ideological forms of administration never accepted as a principle of their doctrine, taxing such an idea as bourgeois.

As there is no perfect system that can meet everyone's demands, on an equal footing [*as advocated by the ideologues of the Soviet Communist Party*], they needed to create an adversary [an enemy of the people] to fight and that, once this monster was defeated, all the problems would be solved. However, as long as this *terrible and astonishing evil* persisted, the long-awaited peace and equality would not be able to be implemented; therefore, it is not the

system's inability to blame, but the bad guys who prevent happiness and peace on Earth, because they want chaos and want to keep privileges only for themselves.

What they do, in fact, is to replace one religion with another, which whoever wants to adhere to, as long as they have it as the sole object of absolute and irresolute adoration, not being divided between faith in a system and a god, because if they don't If so, the question arises "either you are with me, or you are against me!" So this sentence contains a sharp series of secrets that go beyond the very essence that it keeps in itself, apparently naive that it is. More cretin is the disqualified and bad character reporter or historian who attributed this sentence to Major Yuri Gagarin, as a way of disqualifying the first man to fly into space.

It begins that, no blame can be attributed to him for being born and raised in a system like the Soviet one. Once he was there, it was up to him to obey the regime and dedicate himself as a patriot. His religious convictions would in no way prevent him from pursuing a career as a technician, engineer, astronaut, and when the opportunity arose, he was well aware of the risks to which he was subject, even because he had no previous experience on which to base the tests of security, as to their departure from Earth, security in space and return to base. Everything depended on a matter of faith in the technical infallibility of engineers and equipment.

It is rather strange that a man of science, like Major Gagarin, could trust his Soviet Brothers and Comrades so much, without being able to count on any kind of faith that was beyond himself, because he could never return home, as happens in Jules Verne's novel *From Earth to the Moon*, which the Russians knew very well. It was no longer about having faith in the Regime or its Leader; the question was scientific, mechanical, totally subject to failure of all kinds. The first man to see the cosmos in the greatest breadth ever possible for a human must have thought of a number of things, less the inexistence of a Creator for something so perfect. It was there that the Aristotelian theory that the Earth was supported by pillars literally went down the drain, because an eyewitness proved that it was floating in the middle of nowhere, in the void, along with other elements and stars.

He didn't need to have questioned the existence of God, because his testimony already threw down millennia of absurd beliefs that were pushed down the gull, not allowing investigations to be carried out during the longest period of darkness in history imposed by being human, on behalf of a domain project that went [very] right. Naturally, the West, which claims to be Christian, chose Major Russo as its most virulent enemy.

Furthermore, if Major Gagarin were answering a question from Russian Head of State Nikita Khrushchev whether, by some fluke of fate, he had seen God up there in the sky, he still

has a childlike appearance of disappointment. who went to the park and his expectations were not met in the way he had dreamed of.

What is most surprising is that, how can anyone say whether or not they have seen a being that has never been seen by anyone? This is very strange, because, for someone who does not even believe that a certain Being, if God exists, it is far beyond impossible to expect to find him anywhere and not only in space, which only contradicts the discourse ridicule created by the Catholic Church that He would be dwelling in the heavens. It is difficult to know who is in possession of the greatest load of foolishness, since they are plotting a childish game in which each, in their own way, tries to impose their truth on others, not allowing a broad reflection on faith and possibility or not of belief in what cannot be seen, simply because it cannot be determined. When Moses stands before God and questions his identity, who he is, what he calls himself, behold, God answers him: “I am what I am!”²³

In the wake of this affirmation, he tells the prophet that he is the god of Abraham and the god of Israel, that is, he was the only god, the particular god and the municipal god of the Hebrew people and his acceptance would take place through cultural transmission, by faith, by the belief in its power and by the teachings of the fathers, priests and prophets of Judah, not being possible for it to be seen anywhere and would be everywhere, because it was an essential part of the culture and belief of that people.

This is a condition that the *Politburo* never wanted to understand, so possessed that they were by the Marxist ideology of materialism and were unable to understand that Karl Marx himself added an epithet to the term, calling it Dialectical Materialism, or seeking a deeper hermeneutic, an object that dialogues with past and present events, enabling a preview of how actions can be planned for a not too distant future. At no time was Marx so interested in destroying religion, because he knew well that, without it, what did he have to offer in order to fill the empty space that would be left in his absence?

This proved to be the great misfortune of the Soviet Union, the idea of believing that it could supply the entire subjective intellectual *pathological universe* of its compatriots with ideas of equality, forgetting that as soon as the basic needs of humans are satisfied, others arise in the future. place and religion itself had already faced, and the only way he found to hold the dominion for more than a thousand years was through torture and murder, something that

²³ Exodus 13-15: And Moses said to God, Behold, when I come to the children of Israel, and say to them, The God of your fathers has sent me to you; and they say to me: What is your name? What shall I tell them? And God said to Moses: I AM THAT I AM . In: FERREIRA, João Alberto. *Holy Bible*. São Paulo: Bible Society of Brazil, 1969.

Former Seminarian Yosef Stalin learned with painstaking effectiveness, which assured him reach the end of life and die a natural death.

Nikita Khrushchev takes power in the USSR as Stalin's successor, and it seems that the idea of having a Christian in power for decades has opened a wound in Soviet pride that needed to be denied [*not just closed*] at all costs, the which made him put in the mouth of the Major who had just gone to heaven the modest phrase that revealed that God had not been seen in the heavens. The marketing ploy in favor of the Communist Party was the best thought out and all it took was for a Party journalist to try to prove the Leader's thinking that, in a short time, its authorship became an unquestionable truth, reaching the youngest and to westerners on the western side of Europe and the New World as such, worried that everyone was defending themselves from the amazing communism, where people ate helpless little children.

This story may even have its kernel of truth, when Stalin condemned to death, by starvation, the entire people of Ukraine and that, in a single winter, more than a million Ukrainians died, for lack of food and in the following year there were more a million. The event became known as the *Holodomor* what is a word, or a Ukrainian expression, which means to *let die of hunger* , *to die of starvation* . This word came to be used in the context of Ukrainian history to define the events that led to the death by starvation of millions of Ukrainians between 1931 and 1933. “ Progressively, death was accentuated in Ukraine. Between 1931 and 1933, the death toll was so great that the corpses were scattered in the streets and fields. The odor of rotting bodies permeated entire regions. The death toll in those three years is estimated to have been five million. But if you take into account the lingering effects of this perverse economic policy and the Ukrainians who were put into forced labor and died there, that number could be more than 14 million.”²⁴Historian Thomas Woods reiterates this fact: “ *In 1933 Stalin set a new goal of production and collection, which was to be carried out by a Ukraine that was now on the brink of mass death from famine, which had begun in March of that year. year. I will spare the reader the more graphic descriptions of what happened from here. But corpses were everywhere, and the stench of death hung heavily on the air. Cases of insanity, and even cannibalism, are well documented.* ”²⁵

All the insanity and evil of Yosef Stalin served to haunt the former USSR and the history of Russia until the present day and at that moment, when the first human being traveled to outer

²⁴ FERNANDES, Claudio. *Holodomor* . Available at: <https://www.historiadomundo.com.br/idade-contemporanea/holodomor.htm> . Accessed on 01/01/2020.

²⁵ WOODS, Thomas. *The famine in Ukraine* : one of the biggest crimes of the state has been forgotten. Mises Brazil Institute.

space, nothing more opportune than to remove, once and for all, the God who the great dictator believed and that he had not been able to save the Russian people from such contrived violence.

What did not make sense is the fact that a country, avowedly atheist, serves the purpose of discussing the existence of an Entity that, for them, does not exist, or at least they belched their non-belief in it, which remains. It was revealed that his exasperation in denying the existence of God was either sheer folly or fear of the power that religion wielded over mortals. The exaggeration of force in this direction is a demonstration that the interested party to be convinced of this particular truth is the Communist Party and the Politburo itself and not necessarily the Russian people who, as it appears, did not face many problems in this regard and even because he had countless other problems to worry about, such as hunger and the absolute misery that devastated [*almost*] everyone, without the slightest mercy.

It is not surprising that the Soviet Heads of State tried to juggle such an unusual situation and until that exact moment, which would last for almost a decade, they would be the only ones to explore outer space through human beings. Interestingly, Valentina Tereshkova (1937-), the first woman to fly into space, in 1963, did not make any comment in this regard, even because there the dispute was already in another direction, in the case of a war of egos, in which was it sought to stoke the discourse of freedom and liberality enjoyed by American women and which, despite all this arrogance, had what they had to show as a fantastic feat? This is how Khrushchev once again harpooned the American ego.

The internal disputes of the Soviet Union were much more complex than the poets in love with mediocre poetry, where a regime that was never sovereign, not even in the bloc where it was supposed to be absolute sovereign, is supposed. So, I always needed to do something extraordinary from a historical point of view, but without the slightest social relevance, because this helped to divert the focus from domestic failure as politicians, managers and as decent human beings.

Carl Sagan (1934-1996) wrote in 1989 that, man's going to the moon did not represent any kind of relevance for humanity and President Richard Nixon (1913-1994) ends the Apollo Project, because public opinion and the American Congress were not seeing any motivation to continue financing something that had no other purpose than to throw a smokescreen over the real human existential conditions, which was one of insecurity and fear and, while the *soviets* showed their ability to overcome capitalist imperialism, on the other side of the world, Americans showed their resistance to *terror*. It is not known who was more imbecile or who acted more imbecile. What is known is that, in the USA, as it was a democracy, they soon kicked the ass of the gladiators in the fight against the Soviet Monster, because the spectacle of

emotion that took over the televisions in 1969 was, in fact, the music festival that took place at Woodstock Farm in New York and became known as *Woodstock 1969* .

With all the revolution that the *Man on the Moon* may have provoked, the world continued to be more violent and more cretin, with misery rising, the Vietnam War consuming young Americans like flies and, the human being, through his ultra science advanced had managed to explore the skies, but no cures could be found for diseases such as German measles, polio, whooping cough, diphtheria and croup and more, much less any kind of effective and tangible knowledge about the brain and its functioning. and what was most astonishing was the fact that if God were not there in the heavens, where would he be? And, is this question asked because of the shameful war that was being fought in Asia, against the communists? No; not at all! Because there was a just reason for that inglorious battle: the preservation of freedom that was under serious threat and, as it had not been adopted, still the jargon of Democracy, it was she who was at risk, if the *soviets* took control of the world.

HOW MUCH POWER GAGARIN'S EXPRESSION HID

“I went to heaven and didn't see God there!” How much power this speech had coming out of the spirit of someone who had just braved outer space. The self-centered hope of those who stayed here had just taken another hard blow; once again. This is a puerile belief if you consider it so! Judging by what had been said just a few years earlier, in the mid-1950s when Francis Crick (1916-2004) and James Watson (1928-) discovered the helical structure of DNA: “we thought our future was in the stars, but now we know that most of it is within our genes”, this was another ode to exacerbated anthropocentrism.

Well, if the whole adventure of continuing to explore outer space doesn't represent a clear denial of serious and scholarly science, it can only be an iron curtain to hide the inability to know the human spirit [*we prefer to believe it's both*]. But the phrase expressed by the Soviet President hides something much more sinister that Fyodor Dostoyevsky (1821-1881) had already expressed in his unparalleled literary work *The Karamazovi Brothers*, the sentence that *since God does not exist, then everything becomes permitted* . Of course, this phrase is expressed within a lyrical-poetic context; however, when taken in the midst of the desire to build a Machiavellian context, that is, we, those who hold *all* the power in our hands, can do whatever we want, because there is no one who can stop us and/or punish us for what we come to *do* .

All the spotlight was directed, by the cachectic and imbecilid story, on the figure of Major Gagarin and the real monster was obscured, to his complete delight in the situation, because, even if this did not shake the expressed faith of many Christians, the simple The fact that this phrase is repeated over and over after six decades and the subject of in-depth studies, shows that, in the Soviet Union itself, many individuals must have gone to madness, denial and suicide, not so much, out of fear that God, indeed, it might not exist; but because, in an unconscious way, they understood the Dictator's message.

A sentence is never just a sentence! It is and will always be the expression of someone's hidden feeling, revealing a subliminal message, addressed to a specific group. There is no lack of those who say that many historical phrases represented nothing more than rhetorical expressions, euphemisms and things without a causal connection. It happens that the weight and power of a given sentence are in the person who expresses it, regardless of [*or being very unimportant*] the context in which it is applied. Things become more severe if the person who says it is in a position of high power and, to make matters worse, if their decisions become absolute and unquestionable, either out of fear or convenience.

The historical moment in which the sentence, object of study in this work, was uttered is one of those rare moments in which even the context contributed to provoke an uproar of terror and horror that persists throughout history. While the expressions of great impact were in the field of literature and after almost two millennia of the absolute empire of Institutionalized Christianity, man would be further from his faith than when he was in his pagan times, as one likes to belch the devotees. imbeciled by Catholic doctrine.

The 19th century saw the greatest decline of institutionalized blind faith, the one where everything that was considered and validated as being the *truth* was determined by the *religious establishment* . It was not just the great geniuses who had the space to freely publish their ideas, but the Industrial Revolution itself, which is a legacy of the Protestant Revolution of 1517 and Lutheranism. However, ironically, Eastern Europe, which considered itself the most denier of the Christian and divine faith, would be the one who would repeat the feat of Constantine, electing a new prophet on the works of which a new religious doctrine would rise, as or more bloody than Christianity itself: Marxism. And, not satisfied with the results, added by the domain of extreme vanity, other religions emerged, not knowing which of them would prove to be more satanic, to list, Leninism and Stalinism.

The problem with these artificial religions is that they preach equality and universal law, but speak only in the first person, depriving the other of the struggle for the result and of an education for their children and the generation that will succeed them as an inherent process of

development. and preservation of the species, an obligation conferred on man by *Physis* , hence his immense happiness when children arrive; hence the immense happiness of the teacher when new students arrive in search of intellectual formation and so, it happens with the Pastor, the Priest, the Priest, in which each one, in his own way, received a reason to live eternally, linked to someone who , in a natural way, will live beyond itself.

When man is deprived of God, or even of belief in his existence, what will he put in his place? This was the belief of the Communist Party, that they would be those who would be exalted and put in the place of the Most High by the individual himself, by his deliberate will, since they, the Communists, were giving to beings what Divinity had not provided. , but who were entitled to irresolute equality. It happens that, if nobody told them that they had rights, they would live happily with their battles against natural competitors, always at peace with their conditions and as the world advances in the conditions of civilization and enlightenment, they would look for such improvements, not as something conquered by force, but by the courage to desire it and to fight for it.

Major Gagarin was a man of principle, a technician and not a politician from the Politburo clergy, which is enough to deduce that he would not act in such a way as to destroy the faith of good people, if only because he would not see any profit in it. It had broken a millenary taboo and fulfilled a wish of billions of individuals throughout the history of humanity. What more could you want for yourself than a normal, peaceful life?

Putting in his mouth a sentence of such magnitude and weight was the worst crime committed by the Russian President against a civilian, not because of the impact it had on himself, but because of the image of himself that would be projected onto the future and the weight that this would have on the later generations. Even if they are interested in knowing what space looks like from there, the idea that it was he who claimed not *to have seen God up there, in the heavens*, weighs heavily and does not dispel doubt and, religious euphemism aside, destroyed a whole religious discourse whose most sacred mission was to propagate deception and deception on individuals and lead them to a life sustained in misery and exploitation.

The world of faith was never the same after this sentence. Not even the great philosophers of past times [the *overwhelming majority, priests and pastors, therefore, theologians by training*] who fought with the strength they had to shake the bizarre faith implanted by the Catholic Church had the least amount of success that a politician communist of a satanic and cruel regime, putting in the mouth of his greatest prodigy the doubt about the existence of God, where they always said he would be...

There is nothing wrong with human beings seeking to know other universes besides their own, this is part of the process of developing the condition of intellectuality and along with it, comes doubt and curiosity [*in this sequence*], but what can be noticed is that what should be taken as a means, becomes an end... for anything, except to expand the condition of human well-being.

The ancients created totems and images and defined that the particular God or the Municipal God was there and no one dared to enter these instruments in order to prove such a thing, because the belief in that being was worth all personal belief. Modern man, with all his engineering and euphemism, not to mention insecurity and exaggerated vanity have led him to come into conflict with religion, even within his most traditional congregations.

Scientific discoveries, led by serious men and committed to investigative rigor, were dethroning religion from its imaginary axis, and, along with it, the concept of God putting its existence in the cosmos in check. What in the past was explained by faith has been replaced by test tubes and quite palpable demonstrations of how to artificially repeat the feat. Religion never tried to fight socialism because of the evils and oppression it caused on individuals; but purely because it deprived her of her wretched sheep which she took care to treat with the smallest possible crumb of hope. If the Church's aversion was against socialism it would not have gone against the *Welfare state* which is of ideology and creation of the right-wing, capitalist system in favor of the less favored. Because of this contrary position of the Church, feuds between socialist governments and religion were born, leading them to deny any and all types of belief. What she does show is the fact that she fears the assumption that everything that this regime preached could be true and, thus, misery and absolute poverty would disappear, giving rise to the long-awaited kingdom of bonanza, since the only thing that both systems come together well is for the maintenance of the kingdom of hope and paraphrasing the character from the comics Doctor Strange, *of all the evils that can affect the human being to death, hope is the worst* and Nietzsche reveals that Hope is the worst of all evils, because it prolongs human suffering.²⁶

According to Colonel Valentin Petrov, Major Gagarin was baptized in a Russian Orthodox Christian Church. Therefore, a child who is born hearing that God is in heaven, above the clouds, that he does not live in the void, and when, by human force, this child reaches the heights, surpassing the highest clouds, his disappointment begins with the fact that he sees nothing but the extreme void (...); and then, contradicting himself, even more his vain

²⁶ NIETZSCHE, F. *The Gaia Science*. Sao Paulo: Escala, 2006.

expectations do not see God. What a disappointment! His speech expresses another feeling of a teenager when he discovers that his father is not the superman he always dreamed of and believed he could count on. He had been raised in an atheist regime and, possibly for this reason, he despised any kind of belief in the invisible, in what could not be empirically proven. Contrary to what some say that he despised any type of religious belief, I see his expression more as proof of a doubt that they tried to impute to him and that was now crumbling before everyone. The phrase that you heard every Sunday that God was there in Heaven has completely lost its meaning and has become worthless. And, what can be put in its place? This is the big question that frightens individuals who become atheists [*or at least believe in this trickery*]. Nietzsche's question continues to haunt them, like a terrible amalgamation: *How do you live without God?* There is no answer to this question and, sometimes, what is heard is: *one continues to live, as one lives naturally!* This answer remains in the midst of a shrug. But here is another much more complex problem, which is that, in order to live naturally, it is necessary to return to *Physis* , thus denying, no longer to God, but to civilization as such, which leads the human being to a situation like that, to an *existential dead end* .

This loss of the human condition, as we know it, is a blow too hard for a specimen that has come into the world surrounded by countless people who smile with happiness at its arrival, as if it were largely responsible for bringing a special kind of joy that no other would fit such a mission. Suddenly, the whole world turns inside out and there is nothing left that can bring joy, neither to you nor to anyone else, and what remains is pure unhappiness and anguish.

To Nietzsche's question, there is an answer in the form of another question: Wouldn't it be a question about how to live without faith?, for the simple fact that it extends to everything and everyone and not only to the sacred or the numinous Divine, as experience that is lived, that crosses the human being so that it has some meaning; it is an act of meeting the being with your being, allowing you to find a goal to continue in the battle, a battle called life, called existence.

The most serious problem that has taken over the human spirit since time immemorial is vanity and the impossibility of dealing with the brevity of life, confusing it with existence. Generally, in times not insane and managed by insane, the generation that is in charge works for the next generation to be better than its own, to produce results of improvement of the benefits that were produced and above all, to maintain respect for those that preceded them. Nowadays, no matter what happens, the race is to be on the front page of the newspapers, as if this were history and the next day to fight to be on the front page again, because even the concept of history is no longer one based on *Function Quadratic of the Brunner Distance* ;

everything is given in terms of the here and now. In this, the idea of the future disappears and along with it, obviously, the commitment to it, in the same proportion.

It is difficult to translate Khrushchev's thought when saying such a thing and still attribute it to someone who could not even defend himself. For the defense given by his friend, decades later, such a statement bothered the Major, even because it must have been demanded by his companions [*both by those who believed in the existence of God and by those who did not*] and this, in some way, disturbed him, without being able to openly express his dissatisfaction with the situation.

The Soviet regime was a cruel system that did not miss the slightest opportunity to exploit what interested it. Ethics is something they abolished from their primers and the desire for absolute dominion over everything and everyone became the command flag or figurehead that would rule the world from then on. Existence was summed up in this, a binary battle, in which on the one hand, a bunch of imbeciloids tried to implant the kingdom of Eden on Earth, fighting against the imperialism produced by the existence of Capital and what was called conservatism and On the other hand, no less catfish, a fight against terror was advocated, fighting Communism, a system that preached equality for all, without distinction.

It goes without saying that this displeased everyone and it was not because it would take from those who have more to give to those who have less; it was by the simple direction of the policy in which they took the freedom to venture into the expansion of business, curtailing the right to raise new forms of business execution and intellectual investments. On the other hand, there are those who come to expect any kind of help from the State and in a short time begin to demand it and if this does not happen, they rebel, not lacking anyone who says that they are in possession of the legitimate right, because of of a number of factors that are exposed...

Nowhere in the Holy Scriptures is it said that there will be glory without a fight. Man struggles, daily, with nature and all its components, in order to extract his sustenance from there and even his profit that comes from the sale of this surplus to those who are in functions that do not allow them to produce food. This entire endless cycle is governed by a force invisible to human eyes, being present before, during and will persist after the human species ceases to exist, an impossible condition, but hypothetically considered.

Even though *Physis* is violent and imposes on the human being several phenomenological crises of a natural order, which take a good amount of lives, it does not prevent the creation of alternatives and strategies to overcome the challenges that appear each season. With each crisis faced, the intellect is put into action and the result is abstract intelligence being declared in the form of new skills and competences.

The communist religion imposes a disgrace on the individuals whom they call comrades, companions, brothers and at the same time prevents them from seeking a solution and whoever dares to do so is exterminated without the slightest mercy; all in the name of an ideal of collective equality, not social equality.

The religious education that they inculcate in human beings, from birth, transforms them into concrete creatures, incapable of understanding God as essence, this one, also understood under the direction of M. Heidegger's thought, which is the dialectical movement. Even for the intellectual of the 21st century, it is impossible for him to weave a direct spiritual experience with the divine. At school, from Monday to Friday, children hear that everything was created by a God and this is a fait accompli, however, no one has proved it and, as children are in this period of intellectual lethargy, it is better to listen, believe and touch life to forward, after all, they were born into a period of relative peace, where no one dies for believing in these things. Indoctrination from the cradle makes him need a real contact, for this reason, the pastor and/or the priest are holders of such power over their flocks. The prohibition of questioning, a peaceful object of severe punishment, in the same way that doubt is interpreted as blasphemy, an object for which there is no forgiveness, turns those who could go beyond the borders of knowledge in the future into cowards. With this, he condemns the future of all humanity to be managed by gluttons and rogues, if not by cowards who do nothing more than manage by imposing fear on everyone, always looking for easy answers to the problems that arise throughout existence.

Gagarin was a Christian, baptized into the Russian Orthodox Christian Church, and a personal friend of the young man said he never uttered such a phrase; because of being a religious individual. This detail of his life is what reinforces, confirms and validates the said expression. After all, only a very religious man of great faith could have said such a thing because what religious fanatics most expect is that an experience will happen to them that puts them in direct connection with the sacred. And fanaticism is directly proportional to the absence of faith! That is, as the latter decreases, the former rises [*almost*] to the extreme of obsessive madness. The insane desire that a revelation should occur to him is in *itself*, a concrete proof of his doubt about the existence of being, by him, divinized. For this reason, they live immersed in guilt, since it is not sin that gives rise to guilt, but rather this one, which, in order to justify itself, creates the notion of guilt. After all, one is the direct reason for the existence of the other, however, one of them has to come first and, in this way, the vicious cycle of obsessive guilt neurosis makes the individual desecrate his actions, simply, in order to characterize what he feels. and justify that feeling.

Therefore, the defense that I have presented so far and that the research has revealed to be a true premise, that it was not Major Gagarin who expressed the phrase object of study in this work, it was not because he believed that the astronaut was religious, but rather, because this sounded so irrelevant to someone who had just become a living legend that it made no sense to provoke this kind of provocation in relation to the faith of others. What's more, an officer educated in the Soviet military regime learns, first and foremost, to have respect and to be restrained in his actions and words. Not the kind of attitude this sentence expresses!

Any structure that does not have strict control over itself ends up becoming despotic and arbitrary. It was no different with religion... When it appears, it does so as a means, a way for man to use as rites, phrases, libations, songs, all with the aim of connecting, once again, to the invisible and the latter could make himself visible through an answer, which was expected by the suppliant individual. At no time, in its genesis, was it inscribed in some table of law that its use would have as its ultimate end, domination, slavery, subjugation. This came from the petty human feeling that began to take pleasure in that morbid type of power that belief and popular superstition began to attribute to the priest, who began to call himself the direct representative of God on Earth and, later, assumed himself as God himself on Earth.

And it was not the priest's faith that made him all-powerful, it was the popular faith, through a power imputed by the fanciful collective mind, which, little by little, made her believe that, really, that pathetic figure had such power. As this individual came to have a real knowledge of the cycles of nature, impressing the people and elevating himself to the condition of god was [*almost*] ridiculous. He was theatrical amid lightning and thunder and this made him feared and no longer adored by his followers and the next step was to make others adore him, through force and unmeasured brute violence. In short, what was meant to *reconnect* the human being to the sacred began to distance him from him spiritually and the approximation became a euphemism, a lie and an abject power game.

Behold, the problem is not in the religion itself, it is in the people who represent the divine on Earth; because once imbued with extreme power, there is no sensor that is able to stop their greed which becomes schizophrenic, demented and insatiable. At first, the obedience, *in contesti*, of the flock, ecstatic him. But, with time, this is no longer enough for him and so he begins to have the need to test his strength more and more in wider fields and the generalized fear takes over, which leads to a state of disequilibrium such that the solution becomes [*almost*] impossible, allied to the serious problem that the orgasmic ecstasy that the display of this insane power exerts on the unquestioning mind of the population. The priests saw this kind of power bestowed on the bestial beasts and they wanted it for themselves... and they got it!

To public opinion, Major Gagarin said: “I have been to heaven and I have not seen God there!”²⁷ Herodotus could answer him that he did not see him “because, dominated by luck, the gods are so high that they can leave to man, free of hands and thought”²⁸, understanding with this expression, the imagination. Therefore, they imagine that God is in heaven.

When the Church places God in the Heavens, above the highest clouds, it did so because it never thought it possible that, one day, human beings could get there. The Greeks placed their gods on Mount Olympus and at one time the giants of Earth climbed the mount and tried to seize power by brute force. In order to avoid the same disaster, they would place him in a place, eternally, inaccessible to man. And it's not that it went wrong! It worked until the first man got there!

CONCLUSION

The issue surrounding the controversial phrase alleged to have been said by Major Yuri Gagarin is as childish as the very belief that he said it at any time in his life. The exploration of space had already been the work of Jules Verne, published in 1865, but it left astronauts lost in space because it was not known how to bring them back to Earth. This just shows that dreams and desires to accomplish the Soviet feat were already old; however, there was a lack of knowledge and technology to carry them out.

Therefore, when these two limiting factors are overcome, reaching the full realization of the dream and the satisfaction of the desire, the concern is with the existence or not of God inhabiting outer space. Nothing could be more strange and without a causal link with the human conquest that this represents until the present day, given the volume of scientific discoveries, techniques and possibilities of technological and scientific advance experienced.

Discussions and analysis of texts show that Major Yuri Gagarin did not express this thought in relation to the existence of God. Only a very irresponsible individual could have done it, and for this there was no lack of Politburo figures who could put such an expression in the mouth of the Soviet hero.

These distorted situations provoke [*almost*] irreparable distortions in the heroic deeds of great men. It seems that there is a collective interest in reducing contemporary heroes to hideous figures through language structures, creating linguistic stigmas that, once printed, are

²⁷ Gagarin, Yuri (1934-1968). Russian astronaut. The phrase was said, supposedly, by him in 1961.

²⁸In the original: Fortunately, pues, están los dioses tan alto que dejan libres al hombre las manos, y el Pensamiento (HERÓDOTO, 2006, p. 06).

no longer susceptible to being extirpated, in the same way that was the mark imposed on the body of convicts in Greece.